

THE
STASIMOPIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

Compiled by: A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman, C.R. Haddad, S.H. Foord, & L.N. Lotz

South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide Stasimopidae2021 version 1: 1-54

©Johan Richter

THE STASIMOPIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.² & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2021. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Stasimopidae of South Africa* 2021 version 1: 1-54.

¹ARC-Plant Health and Protection, Private Bag X134, Queenswood, Pretoria, 0121, South Africa

²Department of Zoology, University of Venda, Private Bag X5050, Thohoyandou, 0950, South Africa

³Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State, P.O. Box 339, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa

⁴National Museum, Bloemfontein, P.O. Box 266, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa

ABSTRACT

Stasimopidae is monotypic and represented by the genus *Stasimopus* Simon, 1892. It is a southern African endemic represented by 45 species and two subspecies. The genus has not yet been revised and based on the morphological diversity contained within the genus, it is possible that it could be split in to multiple genera at some point in the future (Opatova et al. 2020). According to Hewitt (1915) the characters employed in distinguishing the various species are all somewhat variable, even in specimens taken from the same locality and with the advent of more material from different parts of the country it becomes increasingly difficult to draw a hard and fast line between the various species. Of the 47 *Stasimopus* taxa known from South Africa 46 were South African endemics and 18 Eastern Vape Endemics. Only *Stasimopus fordi* Hewitt, 1927 was also known from Lesotho and Botswana. Only 23 species were known from both sexes and 18 only from the female. *Stasimopus* specimens are difficult to collect and are not well sampled. Twenty-two species are known only from the type locality. Presently only two species are listed as Least Concern due to their wider distribution range and 40 species are data deficient. Only five species are listed of special concern, ranging from Critical Rare (*S. mandelai* Hendrixson & Bond, 2004), Near Threatened (*S. robertsi* Hewitt, 1910), Endangered (*S. filmeri* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012 and *S. griswoldi* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012) and Vulnerable (*S. hewitti* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) Threatened Species Programme; the Universities of the Free State, Venda and Pretoria; the National Research Foundation (NRF) for generously funding and support. The staff of the Arachnology section at the National Collection of Arachnida (Connie Anderson, Petro Marais, Sma Mathebula, Robin Lyle and Annette van den Berg), as well as several volunteers from the public, are thanked for their assistance with the sorting and databasing of specimens collected during the SANSA surveys. Various students, members of the public and the Spider Club of Southern Africa collected material for SANSA. We also thank the South African National Parks and E. Oppenheimer & Son for support and providing opportunity to collect in the parks and reserves as well as the provincial conservation agencies for collecting permits. We are especially thankful to all the photographers who provided photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum without their contribution this guide would have not been possible.

CONTENTS

FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE Bond, Opatova & Hedin, 2020.....4

GENUS STASIMOPUS Simon, 1892.....5

- *Stasimopus artifex* Pocock, 19026
- *Stasimopus astutus* Pocock, 19027
- *Stasimopus bimaculatus* Purcell, 19038
- *Stasimopus brevipalpis* Purcell, 19039
- *Stasimopus caffrus* (C.L. Koch, 1842)10
- *Stasimopus castaneus* Purcell, 190311
- *Stasimopus coronatus* Hewitt, 191512
- *Stasimopus dreyeri* Hewitt, 191513
- *Stasimopus erythrognathus* Purcell, 190314
- *Stasimopus filmeri* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012.....15
- *Stasimopus gigas* Hewitt, 191516
- *Stasimopus grismoldi* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012.....17
- *Stasimopus hewitti* Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012.....18
- *Stasimopus insculptus* Pocock, 1901.....19
- *Stasimopus insculptus peddiensis* Hewitt, 1917.....20
- *Stasimopus kentanicus* Purcell, 1903.....21
- *Stasimopus kolbei* Purcell, 190322
- *Stasimopus leipoldti* Purcell, 1902.....23
- *Stasimopus longipalpis* Hewitt, 1917.....24
- *Stasimopus mandelai* Hendrixson & Bond, 2004.....25
- *Stasimopus maraisi* Hewitt, 191426
- *Stasimopus meyeri* (Karsch, 1879)27
- *Stasimopus minor* Hewitt, 191528
- *Stasimopus nanus* Tucker, 1917.....29
- *Stasimopus nigellus* Pocock, 1902.....30
- *Stasimopus obscurus* Purcell, 190831
- *Stasimopus oculatus* Pocock, 1897.....32-33
- *Stasimopus palpiger* Pocock, 1902.....34
- *Stasimopus patersonae* Hewitt, 191335

- *Stasimopus poweri* Hewitt, 191536
- *Stasimopus purcelli* Tucker, 191737
- *Stasimopus quadratimaculatus* Purcell, 190338
- *Stasimopus qumbu* Hewitt, 191339
- *Stasimopus robertsi* Hewitt, 191040
- *Stasimopus rufidens* (Ausserer, 1871)41
- *Stasimopus schoenlandi* Pocock, 190042
- *Stasimopus schreineri* Purcell, 190343
- *Stasimopus schultzei* Purcell, 190844
- *Stasimopus spinipes* Hewitt, 191745
- *Stasimopus spinosus* Hewitt, 191446
- *Stasimopus steynburgensis* Hewitt, 191547
- *Stasimopus suffuscus* Hewitt, 191648
- *Stasimopus tysoni* Hewitt, 191949
- *Stasimopus umtaticus* Purcell, 190350
- *Stasimopus umtaticus ranger* Hewitt, 1927.....51
- *Stasimopus unispinosus* Purcell, 190352

REFERENCES.....53-54

Stasimopus female after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997).

FAMILY STASIMOPIDAE Bond, Opatova & Hedin, 2020

Stasimopidae is a new family by Bond, Opatova & Hedin, in Opatova et al. (2020), including only the genus *Stasimopus* Simon, 1892.

COMMON NAME: Cork-lid Trapdoor spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 15-43 mm (males smaller and more slender). Colour varies from brown to reddish black with legs yellowish brown or reddish brown, abdomen usually a palid duller colour. Carapace domed and smooth without setae with the fovea procurved; eyes 8 in 2 rows (4:4), anterior row usually procurved. Abdomen oval and covered with a thin layer of short setae. Legs short, strong and thickly spined and tibiae III cylindrical without dorsal saddle-shaped depression, distal segments of legs I and II with lateral bands of short thorn-like spines setae in the female.

LIFE STYLE: Ground dwellers that live in a burrow that is closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. They use their rastellums to dig tube-like burrows of various shapes and depths (14-20 cm deep). The burrow is lined with a layer of felt-like silk. They close the burrows off from the outside with well fitting, hinged trapdoors of variable thickness. The trapdoor is made of soil, often clay, modeled into shape and reinforced with silk. It resembles a cork of a bottle, hence the common name. The lid is attached to the entrance rim of the burrow by a tough silk hinge. The outside of the trapdoor is usually very well camouflaged, as it is made of the same soil as the surrounding area. The lid is provided with a circle of small pits on the inside to provide the spider with a place to grip. When disturbed the spider pulls the lid close and holds it down with the strong setae on the front legs. The trapdoor is used as a protection-prey-detection system. Usually during the day, while resting in the bottom of the burrow the lids are kept close. It is also kept close during harsh weather, moulting and egg laying. Most of the trapdoor spiders are nocturnal and they open the trapdoor slightly waiting for prey to pass close to the burrow. The spider then rushes out, grabs the prey and returns to the burrow. They are usually found in open areas in Grassland, Savanna, Nama-Karoo and Succulent-Karoo biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The genus has not yet been revised and based on the morphological diversity contained within the genus, it is possible that *Stasimopus* could be split in to multiple genera at some point in the future (Opatova et al. 2020). According to Hewitt (1915) the characters employed in distinguishing the various species are all somewhat variable even in specimens taken from the same locality and with the advent of more material from different parts of the country it becomes increasingly difficult to draw a hard and fast line between the various species.

Closed burrow

Underside of trapdoor

Open burrow entrance

Stasimopus sp. female Photo Peter Webb

Stasimopus sp. male Photo david Jacobs

GENUS STASIMOPUS Simon, 1892

Stasimopus was transferred from Ctenizidae to Stasimopidae by Opatova et al. (2020). It is represented by 45 species and two subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2021).

COMMON NAME: Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Stasimopus caffrus* (C. L. Koch, 1842)

MORPHOLOGY: According to Raven (1985) and summarized by Engelbrecht and Prendini (2012), *Stasimopus* can be distinguished on the basis of the following combination of unique characters: (1) lacking a saddle like depression on tibia III; (2) having a very wide eye group (twice as wide as it is long); and (3) palpal endites with a modified anterior lobe.

Female body stout, thick-set; smooth with shiny areas; cephalic region domed; eyes in two rows, posterior row wider than anterior row; anterior lateral eyes larger than anterior median eyes; posterior median eyes oval, widely spaced close to posterior lateral eyes; fovea strongly procurved; cheliceral furrow with two rows of teeth; sternum triangular, posterior edge truncated with one shallow sternal sigilla posteriorly; sternum and labium fused; rastellum thick spines. Abdomen round oval, with dense layer short setae. Legs stout; curved spinules present on lateral faces of anterior pairs of legs of the female. Male smaller, slender with long legs; darker in colour; carapace with three keels that can reach back so far as the fovea; the surface more or less lightly sculptured or roughened throughout, being nowhere quite smooth.

LIFESTYLE: *Stasimopus* species live in silk-lined burrows that are usually made in flat areas. Females and juveniles only leave their burrows to capture prey that are within reach of the burrow entrance. Adult males are more slender with longer legs and usually wander around in search of a female. Published information on the burrows and trapdoors of some *Stasimopus* species is summarized in Dippenaar-Schoeman (2002: 33). Bold (2008) found in a village in the former Ciskei that *Stasimopus* spiders are used by the Xhosas to hunt. Apparently the spider is killed, dried and crushed and mixed with the hunting dog's food before a hunt. This makes the dog quicker and more alert. The same is given to watchdogs. The Xhosa name for the spider is "itoyitoti."

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Genus not yet revised. According to Hewitt (1915), most of the species are confined to the Cape provinces and the Free State. The more northern provinces have only lately been surveyed by Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012) and Neethling & Haddad (2019).

Stasimopus sp. showing domed cephalic region, wide eye region and spinules on front legs Photo Peter Webb

Stasimopus sp. Female Photo Les Oates

Stasimopus artifex Pocock, 1902

COMMON NAMES: Grahamstown Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Cuyler-ville, near Grahamstown. The species is known from three localities sampled prior to 1902 (EOO= 571 km²; EOO= 49 km²; 242 m a.s.l.). It is suspected to be under collected since trapdoor spiders are not easy to locate. Identification of the species is still problematic, and some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Bathurst, Rokeby Park (-33.5, 26.84); Bathurst, Pigs Island (-33.4838, 26.8320); Seaview (-34.01, 25.38); Grahamstown, Cuyler-ville (-33.49, 27.02).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a thick lid. Sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is likely to be threatened by loss of habitat due to urbanization (Bathurst and Sea View) and also crop farming (Bathurst). Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Stasimopus artifex female from Pigs Island
Photos John Richter

***Stasimopus astutus* Pocock, 1902**

COMMON NAME: Pearston Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Pearston. Known from three localities (EOO= 2 069 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 415-736 m a.s.l.). It is suspected to be under collected since trapdoor spiders are not easy to locate. It is under collected and more localities are suspected to occur. Identification of the species is problematic, and some more sampling is needed to determine the species' present range. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Pearston (-32.59, 25.15); Bedford (-32.68, 26.08); Jansenville (-32.93, 24.67).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a thick trapdoor lid. Known from the Thicket and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no obvious threats to the species. Identification of the species is problematic, and some more sampling is needed to determine the species' present range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Female total length 35 mm.

***Stasimopus bimaculatus* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAME: Karoo Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1903) from Willowmore. Known from three provinces including (EEO=47 031 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 837-1375 m a.s.l.). Although identification of the male is still problematic, the species' range of the female is wide and therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park Lammetjiesleegte (-32.3317, 22.5483).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living. Live in silk-lined burrows closed with a thick trapdoor lid. Sampled from the Nama Karoo and Grassland biomes (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Colour brown, the carapace behind and the two posterior pairs of legs paler and more yellowish, the pedipalps ochraceous above along the middle of the patella and tibia, the two posterior pairs of legs and the 4 pairs of coxae pale ochraceous ; abdomen pallid, with a small black dorsal patch in front and a larger one behind (Purcell 1903).

Stasimopus brevivalpis Purcell, 1903

COMMON NAMES: Ashton Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1903) from Ashton. Known from three localities collected prior to 1903 (EOO= 296 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 108 -227 m a.s.l.). Identification of the species is still problematic, some more sampling is needed to determine the species' present range and it is therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Ashton: Farm Bonnie Vale (-33.94, 20.07); Robertson (-33.8, 19.87); Bontebok National Park (-34.0708, 20.4756).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a trapdoor lid with a width of 22 mm and hinge width of 15 mm and the average thickness of lid is 4 mm. The width of burrow lower down is 16.8 mm. Burrows have been found in the Fynbos Biome (Purcell 1903).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threatened by loss of habitat for crop farming (Bonnievale) and habitat degradation due to soil erosion along the banks of Breede River. Protected in the Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Stasimopus brevivalpis Photo Peter Webb

***Stasimopus caffrus* (C.L. Koch, 1842)**

COMMON NAME: Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by C.L. Koch (1842) as *Actinopus caffrus*. Known only from type locality stated as Cape of Good Hope (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 333 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: type locality only as Cape of Good Hope

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows in the Fynbos Biomes, closed with a thick trapdoor lid.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from a female.

Habitus and eye pattern after C.L. Koch (1842)

***Stasimopus castaneus* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAME: Port Elizabeth Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1903) from Port Elizabeth (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 17 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows sampled in the Thicket Biome, closed with a thick trapdoor lid.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There has been extensive habitat loss to urban development at the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from a female. Carapace dark brown, only slightly paler posteriorly; chelicerae, pedipalpi, and legs dark reddish brown, the two posterior pairs of legs paler and more yellowish below; sternum dark brown, pale yellowish posteriorly; abdomen dirty yellowish (Purcell 1903).

Stasimopus coronatus Hewitt, 1915

COMMON NAME: Kroonstad Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Hewitt (1915) from Kroonstad. Known from four provinces (EEO= 20 011 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 1289-1797 m a.s.l.). Identification of species is still problematic. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Kroonstad (-27.65, 27.24). **Gauteng:** Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-26.14; 27.86). **Limpopo:** Ellisras/Lephalale (-27.71, 23.32); **North West:** Mafeking (-25.82, 25.63).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in a silk-lined burrow closed with a round cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown. Protected in the Kloofendal Nature Reserve. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace and appendages dark castaneous. Abdomen pale above, only infuscated mesially behind, and dorsally over a narrow median area. Patch of red spinules on anterior surface of patella IV extending over about 1/4 of the length of the anterior surface; tibia I very slightly shorter than metatarsus I. Total length 37 mm (Hewitt 1915). First *Stasimopus* record from Limpopo.

Stasimopus coronatus female from Lephalale Photos Peter Webb

***Stasimopus dreyeri* Hewitt, 1915**

COMMON NAMES: Dreyer's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Free State endemic described by Hewitt (1915) from Kroonstad (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 1374 m a.s.l.). Known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State*: Kroonstad (-27.65, 27.24).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a round cork-lid trapdoor in the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by habitat loss for urbanization and possibly crop farming in the surrounding areas. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' present range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from a female. Carapace castaneous, appendages dark, abdomen somewhat influscated over the median area above. Total length 36 mm (Hewitt 1915).

Stasimopus erythrognathus Purcell, 1903

COMMON NAMES: Worcester Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described Purcell (1903) from Worcester (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 244 m a.s.l.). Known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' present range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid width is 30 mm with hinge width of 6 mm and the average thickness of lid is 4.5 mm. The upper part of burrows are more funnel-shaped Purcell (1903). Sampled in the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There has been extensive loss of habitat due to urbanization and agriculture at the type location. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' present range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Female carapace brown, yellowish posteriorly; chelicerae reddish brown; pedipalpi and legs brown, the two posterior pairs yellowish below and also in places above; coxae of legs and posterior part of sternum more or less ochraceous; coxa of pedipalp reddish; anterior part of sternum fuscous brown; abdomen dirty pale yellowish, with broad dark patch above along the middle; posterior lateral eyes much larger than the medians. Total length 36 mm (Purcell 1903). Male carapace and appendages brown, without infuscation except to a slight extension of the ocular area: tibia of pedipalps pale. Abdomen dark above, pale below. Coxae of pedipalps and first two pairs of legs inferiorly castaneous; otherwise the legs are brown below like the sternum (Hewitt 1914).

Burrow entrance after Purcell (1903).

Stasimopus erythrognathus male from Worcester Photos ASD

Stasimopus filmeri Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012

COMMON NAMES: Horned Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: EN

NATIONAL CRITERIA

B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012) from the Krugersdorp district. Known from two provinces (EOO= 190 km²; AOO= 20 km²; 1245-1398 m a.s.l.) and recorded from fewer than five locations. There is ongoing loss of habitat in parts of its range due to urban development and crop cultivation it is therefore listed as Endangered under criterion B.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Mohalesgate, Hekpoort (-25.9307, 27.6425). **North West:** Broederstroom Farm Karee-oorde, 1 km SW of (-25.856, 27.71443); Broederstroom (-25.8019, 27.87591); Hartebeesfontein Conservancy, Farm Hartebeest 1 (-25.71085, 27.95386); Hartebeesfontein Conservancy, Farm Hartebeest 2 (-25.8451, 27.65984); Hartebeesfontein Mokoya Lodge (-25.84457, 27.6604).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat to urban development and crop farming around Hartebeespoort. More sampling needed to determine the full range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Stasimopus filmeri female Photo Neila du Preez

Stasimopus filmeri female Photo Neila du Preez

Stasimopus filmeri female Photo P. Hawkes

Stasimopus filmeri male Photo D. Jacobs

***Stasimopus gigas* Hewitt, 1915**

COMMON NAMES: Venterskroon Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A North West endemic described by Hewitt (1915) from Venterskroon. Presently known only from two localities (EOO < 100 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 1343-1418 m a.s.l.) sampled prior to 1915. Identification of the species is, however, still problematic and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State:* Vredefort, Barrett-Hamilton (-27.01, 27.37).

North West: Vredefort road, Venterskroon (-26.83, 27.31).

LIFESTYLE: Live in silk-lined burrows sampled from the Grassland Biome. Closed with a cork-lid trapdoor.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality has an ongoing threat of habitat loss due to crop farming. the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Total length 36 mm.

Stasimopus griswoldi Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012

COMMON NAMES: Griswold's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Endangered

NATIONAL CRITERIA: B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONAL: A North West endemic described by Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012) from the Brits district. Known from fewer than five locations (EOO= 95 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 1187-1389 m a.s.l.) and experiencing ongoing loss of habitat to crop cultivation and urban development, this species qualifies as Endangered under the B criterion.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: North West: Kommandonek S slopes of Magaliesberg at Kommandonek (-25.748, 27.817); Hartebeesfontein Conservancy, Farm Hartebeest (-25.8749, 27.7568); Hekpoort Farm Hartebeesfontein 473 (-25.835, 27.654); Kommandonek (-25.7367, 27.8189).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid door. Sampled from the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Although approximately 46% of the habitat in the valley inhabited by this species has been transformed, primarily for agriculture, the species appears to persist on relatively small patches of natural habitat, especially in rocky areas unsuitable for agriculture. Habitat destruction associated with urban and infrastructural developments spreading westward from the recreational areas around Hartebeespoort Dam, however, represents an ongoing threat to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Female chelicerae uniformly black. Leg III metatarsus black proximally; leg IV metatarsus mostly black, becoming paler distally. Book lung covers yellow or black; anterior pair always pale, posterior pair black in some specimens; genital plate, between anterior book lungs, paler than rest of abdomen or similar in color to pale book lung coverings, creating pale band across antero-ventral part of abdomen.

Male and female after Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012)

Stasimopus hewitti Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012

COMMON NAMES: Hewitt's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU **NATIONAL CRITERIA:** B1ab(i,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Gauteng endemic described Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012 from the Wonderboom district. Presently recorded from seven locations (EOO= 4 910 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 1142-1618 m a.s.l.). There is ongoing loss of habitat within this species range to urbanization, and it is therefore listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Eldoraigne, Centurion (-25.8378, 28.1518); Gesina, Pretoria (-25.71899, 28.2053); Grand Central of airport complex (-25.997, 28.138); Hartebeeshoek (-25.8839, 27.70805); Olympus, Pretoria Plot 6 (-25.8086, 28.3419); Pretoria/Tshwane Roodeplaat, 14 mi. NE of Pretoria (-25.612, 28.361); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.6224, 28.3683); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve Area W of Aqua Land(-25.632, 28.357); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, West (-25.6416, 28.3610); Roodeplaat, 14 miles NE of Pretoria (-26.6117, 28.3613); Swavelpoort, near Willows, East of Pretoria (-25.8564, 28.3881); Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve (-25.4176, 28.0830); Zeekoegat, near Roodeplaat (-25.613, 28.3221).

LIFESTYLE: Ground burrow dwellers. The species occurs in a wide range of habitats and soil types, and appears to be absent only from very sandy soils. Sampled from the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: About 50% of the species range has been transformed for infrastructure and housing development. Protected in the Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve and Tswaing Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Female medium-sized spiders (carapace length, 8–12 mm). Male carapace black; legs I–IV, metatarsi and tarsi red, IV occasionally black proximally; rest of legs and pedipalps black; abdomen, ventral and lateral surfaces black, dorsal surface powder blue; book lung covers yellow. Female resemble *S. robertsi*.

Stasimopus hewitti male Photo David Jacobs

Stasimopus hewitti female and male after Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012)

Stasimopus insculptus Pocock, 1901

COMMON NAMES: Eastern Cape Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described Pocock (1901) from King William's Town. Presently known from three localities in a restricted range (EEO= 465 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 349-1257 m a.s.l.) and sampled prior to 1901. Identification of the species is still problematic and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: King Williamstown (Pirie Forest) (-32.72, 27.24); Peddie (-33.19, 27.12); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Species is still problematic and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Male with carapace and mouthparts black; legs deep brown with reddish-yellow tarsi and metatarsi; abdomen yellowish brown. Total length 16 mm (Pocock 1901).

Stasimopus insculptus female Photo T. Bold

Stasimopus insculptus peddiensis Hewitt, 1917

COMMON NAMES: Peddies Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described Hewitt (1917) from Peddie (EOO<100 km²) and sampled in 1916. Identification of the species is still problematic and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Peddie (-33.19, 27.12).

LIFESTYLE:: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Species is still problematic and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Male with carapace and mouth-parts black; legs deep brown with reddish-yellow tarsi and metatarsi; abdomen yellowish brown. Total length 16 mm (Hewitt 1917).

Palp after Hewitt (1917)

Stasimopus insculptus peddiensis male and female after Hewitt (1917)

***Stasimopus kentanicus* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAMES: Kentani Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1903) from type locality Kentani (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 485 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality, its status remains obscure and some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Kentani (-32.5, 28.32).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid is thick with the underside unevenly convex and strongly rounded at edges. The circle of pits almost entirely obliterated (Purcell 1903). Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality has a loss of habitat threat due to infrastructure development, and habitat degradation due to cattle farming. Status remains obscure and some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

***Stasimopus kolbei* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAMES: Kolbe's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1903) and known only from the type locality Kentani (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 9 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range, therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Qoloro River Mouth, Kentani (-32.5, 28.32).

LIFESTYLE: Live in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid door. The lid is thick and cork-shaped with a broad hinge. The peripheral surface strongly marked and lid edge scarcely bevelled, except on hinge side. The underside flattened with pits almost obliterated. (Purcell, 1903; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002). Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality has a habitat degradation threat due to cattle grazing. Therefore the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female.

***Stasimopus leipoldti* Purcell, 1902**

COMMON NAMES: Leipoldt's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described Purcell (1902) from the type locality, collected around 1900 in Clanwilliam, an urbanized area surrounded by crop farming (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 83 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female.

Stasimopus longipalpis Hewitt, 1917

COMMON NAMES: Long Palp Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Hewitt (1917) from Kimberley an area threatened by loss of habitat due to mining and urbanization (EOO<1000 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 1217 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality has a habitat loss threat due to urbanization and mining activities.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male. Carapace dark brown to pale brown; legs also brown, the two anterior pairs and the palp being somewhat darker than the hinder two pairs, except the distal portions of those appendages, are pale. Total length 11 mm (Hewitt 1917).

After Hewitt (1917)

Stasimopus longipalpis male from Kalkfontein Dam NR
Photo Nicolette Josling

Stasimopus longipalpis male Photo Allen Jones

Stasimopus mandelai Hendrixson & Bond, 2004

COMMON NAMES: Mandela's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Critically Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hendrixson & Bond, (2004) and known only from the type locality, the Great Fish River Nature Reserve (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 323 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range and being only known from one protected subpopulation it is listed as Critically Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Great Fish River Nature Reserve (-33.13, 26.65).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. A few specimens were sampled from the type locality. One female with 35 second instar spiderlings. Type locality fall within the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: It is only known from one protected subpopulation. More sampling needed to determine the range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

After Hendrixson & Bond, (2004)

Stasimopus maraisi Hewitt, 1914

COMMON NAMES: Marais's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Hewitt (1914) from Victoria West. Presently known from two provinces (EOO= 278 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 588-1270 m a.s.l.). Identification of the species is problematic and the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Farm Driefontein, 12 m from Victoria West (-31.4, 23.12). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.49414, 21.08804).

LIFESTYLE: Sampled from the Fynbos and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Presently it is protected in the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999) but the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The small size of the posterior lateral eyes is perhaps the most striking feature of the species in both sexes. Female carapace and appendages pale brown above, the chelicerae rather more deeply coloured; abdomen pale above with some dark blotches which in the hinder half are symmetrically arranged, forming a kind of tree pattern. Total length 32.5 (Hewitt 1914). Male carapace with a tuft of hairs over the ocular area: the 3 usual keels present, the median one which carries hairs, extending to the fovea. (Hewitt 1927)

Patch of red spinules on anterior part of patella

Eye pattern after Hewitt (1914)

Stasimopus maraisi female from Aardvark NR Photo Peter Webb

***Stasimopus meyeri* (Karsch, 1879)**

COMMON NAME: Meyer's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Karsch (1879) as *Moggridgea meyeri* and known only from the Hantam district (no exact locality). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Hantam district no exact locality.

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Stasimopus minor Hewitt, 1915

COMMON NAMES: Minor Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Free State endemic described by Hewitt (1915) from Bloemfontein. Presently known from four localities (EOO= 3 042 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 1357-1663 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free State: Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); National Botanical Garden (-29.11, 26.22).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Neethling & Haddad (2019) sampled 25 specimens over a period of 10 months from the Free State National Botanical Garden, and found that average maximum daily temperature had a significant effect on the activity pattern of the species. It was only active in autumn, from mid-March to the end of May, when the study ended. The type locality was in the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. It is protected in the Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2018), Free State National Botanical Garden (Neethling & Haddad 2019) and Mpetsane Conservation Estate (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the male. The female has been collected but not yet described.

Stasimopus minor male from Bloemfontein Botanical Garden Photos C. Haddad

***Stasimopus nanus* Tucker, 1917**

COMMON NAMES: Smithfield Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Free State endemic described by Tucker (1917) and only known from type locality Smithfield, an area threatened by loss of habitat due to urbanization and agricultural activity (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 1405 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State*: Smithfield (-30.21, 26.53).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dwellers living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality has a low level threat of loss of habitat to housing development.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female.

***Stasimopus nigellus* Pocock, 1902**

COMMON NAMES: Vredeford Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1902) from the Vredeford Road in the Free State. It is presently known from two provinces (EOO<500 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 1349-1563 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Vredeford Road, Venterskroon (-26.83, 27.31). **North West:** Potchefstroom (-26.7, 27.09).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Male jet-black, with the tarsi and distal end of the metatarsi yellowish red ; paler brownish beneath, the genital plate and opercula testaceous; carapace coarsely rugose, TL 9 mm (Pocock 1902). Female carapace castaneous; abdomen pale above only infuscated mesially behind, TL 36 mm (Hewitt 1915).

***Stasimopus obscurus* Purcell, 1908**

COMMON NAMES: Namakwa Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1908) from a type locality given only as Little Namaqualand ((Dr. S c h u l t z e states that he is not absolutely certain that the locality is correct). It was also sampled from the Free State (EOO < 1000 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 951-1400 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* type locality only "Little Namaqualand". *Free State:* Reddersburg (-29.64, 26.15).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only the female. Colour of carapace and limbs brown, the two posterior pairs of legs being lighter; abdomen black, paler below; leg 4 with a large patch of red spinules on the patella, occupying over 3/4 of the length of the anterior surface. TL (including chelicera) 24 mm (Purcell 1908).

Stasimopus oculatus Pocock, 1897

COMMON NAMES: Common Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Pocock (1897) from Bloemfontein. The species have a wide distribution and was sampled from five provinces (EOO= 168 004 km²; AOO= 72 km²; 397-1628 m a.s.l.). The species has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek)(-28.83, 26.08); Edenville (Farm Lusthof) (-27.55, 27.66); Bredell, 15 km S Ventersburg (-27.65, 27.24); Kroonstad (-27.65, 27.24); Reddersburg (-29.64, 26.15); Jagersfontein (-29.74, 25.43); Ladybrandt (-29.19, 27.45); Winburg (-28.49, 27.00); Venterskroon (-26.83, 27.31); Free State National Botanical Garden (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane: CSIR (-25.74, 28.19); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.2); Wallmannsthal (-25.52, 28.3); Kameeldrift-East (-25.74, 28.19); Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75); Standerton (-26.94, 29.23). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32). **Mpumalanga:** Standerton (-26.94, 29.23). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76). **North West:** Magaliesberg, Mount Grace (-20.97, 31.65); Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.75).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid is thick, D-shaped with bevelled edge. The burrow width 30–60 mm at entrance, lower down 23–50 mm and it is thickly lined with silk. The upper surface of lid coated with mud (Pocock, 1897). Neethling & Haddad (2019) sampled 48 specimens over a period of 10 months from the Free State National Botanical Garden, and found that average minimum daily temperature had a significant effect on the activity pattern of the species. It was active from mid-November to the end of March. It was found associated with termite (*Trinervitermis trinervoides*) in the Free State (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006). Sampled from the Grasland and savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011, Haddad et al. 2013)

Stasimopus oculatus female from Bloemfontein Photo Charles Haddad

Burrow entrance Photo Charles Haddad

Stasimopus oculatus female from Bloemfontein Photo Rudi Steenkamp

After Pocock (1897)

Stasimopus oculatus (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats. It is protected in the Er-fenisdam Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2015), Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler 2019), Groenkloof Nature Reserve, Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989) and Free State National Botanical Garden (Neethling & Haddad 2019).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. The female carapace yellowish brown; legs and chelicerae slightly darker; chelicerae with copper-red setae near extremity; dorsal surface of abdomen pale with a dark mesial purplish blotch; TL female 30 mm (Pocock 1897). Male has been collected but not yet described (Neethling & Haddad, 2019).

Stasimopus oculatus female from Bloemfontein Photo Rudi Steenkamp

Female from Bloemfontein Photo Rudi Steenkamp

Undescribed male from Bloemfontein Photo Charles Haddad

Stasimopus palpiger Pocock, 1902

COMMON NAMES: Graaff-Reinet Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Pocock (1902), only known from type locality Graaff-Reinet, an area that has lost some habitat to housing development (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 746 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range, therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Graaf Reinet (-32.24, 24.53).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality has a moderate but ongoing decline of suitable habitat due to housing development. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male, with male palp illustrated.

Palp after Pocock (1902)

***Stasimopus patersonae* Hewitt, 1913**

COMMON NAMES: Paterson's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1913) from Port Elizabeth. Known from a restricted range with all the specimens sampled prior to 1913 (EOO=230 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 5-311 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Alicedale (-33.31, 26.08); Perseverence Uitenhage Road, Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Redhouse (-33.82, 25.55).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a D-shaped cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for infrastructure development in Port Elizabeth and Alicedale. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes, not illustrated. Female carapace and appendages very dark brown, almost black, the abdomen fuscous; lower surfaces dark brown; patch of red spinules on patella IV not very large, only conspicuous over about half the segment though scattered spines extend almost to the distal margin (Hewitt 1913).

***Stasimopus poweri* Hewitt, 1915**

COMMON NAMES: Kimberley Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1915) and only known from type locality, Modder River near Kimberley in an area threatened by loss of habitat due to urbanization and farming activity (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²;1116 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range, therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Modder River near Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is potentially threatened by loss of habitat to infrastructure development and farming activity in Modder River. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female.

Stasimopus purcelli Tucker, 1917

COMMON NAMES: Purcell's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1917) and known only from Caledon, an area threatened by loss of habitat mainly due to agricultural activities (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 217 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Caledon (-34.24, 19.43).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality and surrounding areas are threatened by loss of habitat due wheat farming and housing development. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

Palp after Tucker (1917)

***Stasimopus quadratimaculatus* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAMES: Four-spotted Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described Purcell (1903) from the Hot Baths near Montagu. Known only from type locality, an area threatened by loss of habitat due to urbanization and agricultural activity (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 268 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid is very thick (5.5–9 mm), cork-like and not strongly bevelled at the edge with lower edge more angular. Burrow width at entrance 23–28 mm while width narrowed to 16–18 mm. The depth of the burrow 18–19 cm (Purcell 1903). Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The type locality is threatened by loss of habitat due to infrastructure development and farming activities around Montagu. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female.

***Stasimopus qumbu* Hewitt, 1913**

COMMON NAMES: Qumbu Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1913) and known only from type locality, Qumbu (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 950 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Farm Shawbury, Qumbu (-31.16, 28.86).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled in the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. Female carapace and legs dark chestnut brown above, pale beneath; abdomen fuscous above, yellowish below. The patch of red spinules on patella IV rather small, dorsally covering less than half the length of the segment absence of apical spinules on the tibia of the pedipalp. Length of carapace 12.5 mm (Hewitt 1913).

Stasimopus robertsi Hewitt, 1910

COMMON NAMES: Roberts' Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: NT NATIONAL CRITERIA B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Hewitt (1910) from Mayville, Pretoria. Known from between 10 and 15 extant locations from two provinces (EOO= 9 344 km²; AOO= 80 km²; 1213-1692 m a.s.l.). It is threatened by ongoing loss of habitat for infrastructure development in parts on its range, with approximately 83% of its habitat irreversibly transformed.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Hewitt's (1910) description of *S. robertsi* was based on females collected from several localities around Pretoria by A. Roberts and G.P.F. van Dam of the Transvaal Museum. According to Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012) the identity of female material from localities at which males were not collected is uncertain. Only the localities listed by them are listed here: **Gauteng:** Faerie Glen Nature Reserve, Pretoria (-25.7707, 28.3008); Hatfield, Pretoria (-25.7434, 28.2381); Magaliesberg, Wonderboom Poort (-25.69, 28.20).

Unverified Records: The following material, identified as *S. robertsi* mostly by Hewitt (1916), was examined, but the identifications cannot be verified until adult males are collected in the vicinity (Engelbrecht and Prendini 2012). Garsfontein, Pretoria (-25.7936, 28.3001); Lyttelton Junction (-25.831, 28.208); Skinners Court, Pretoria (-25.746, 28.229); between Villieria and Derdepoort Pretoria (-25.706, 28.26); Bon Accord Siding (-25.625, 28.203); Pretoria North (-25.74, 28.19); Rosslyn, Akasia (-25.622, 28.0865) Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012)

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in burrows usually made in hard, bare ground, sometimes associated with grass under rocks. The burrow is closed with a lid 6 mm thick with distinct pits on lid. The burrow is vertical with width at top 25 mm, width at bottom 28 mm. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes. However, two males of *S. robertsi* were collected from burrows with lids that closely resembled those of the female, but smaller (Hewitt 1916).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for urbanization but more sampling needed especially to find the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Engelbrecht and Prendini (2012). Known from both sexes.

Stasimopus robertsi female and male after Engelbrecht & Prendini (2012)

Stasimopus rufidens (Ausserer, 1871)

COMMON NAMES: Durban Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Ausserer (1871) as *Cyrtocarenum rufidens* from Port Natal (Durban). Known from three localities with most of the specimens sampled prior to 1898 (EOO= 1 761 km²; AOO=12 km²; 148-1447 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Mooirivier (-29.2, 30); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Savanna biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for urbanization around Durban and crop farming around Estcourt. It is protected in the Phinda Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from only the female. Carapace dark brown, shiny. The abdomen is short-oval, very convex, of a mouse-colour, clothed with very short hairs. The legs are short, very strong, 4, 1,3, 2, similar in colour to the cephalothorax, furnished with hairs, and numerous short strong spines near the sides of the tarsi and metatarsi of the first and second pairs (O. Pickard-Cambridge 1889).

After O. Pickard-Cambridge (1889)

Stasimopus burrow entrance at Phinda NR Photo Elsa van Niekerk

Stasimopus schoenlandi Pocock, 1900

COMMON NAMES: Schoenland's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Pocock (1900) from Middleton. Presently known from several localities but all of them sampled prior to 1913 (EOO= 15 531 km²; AOO= 28 km²; 7-737 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the present species range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Jansenville (-32.93, 24.67); Brak Kloof (-33.53, 26.5); Atherstone Station (-33.19, 26.23); Somerset East (-32.73, 25.6); Middledrift (-32.82, 26.98); Middleton (-32.92, 25.82); Kamacks road near Uitenhage (-33.76, 25.39); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Debe Neck (-32.49, 27.09).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the present species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Stasimopus schoenlandi female SANSA VMus

Stasimopus schreineri Purcell, 1903

COMMON NAMES: Schreiner's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1903 from Hanover. Presently known from two provinces with all records collected prior to 1903 (EOO= 13 509 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 7-1358 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the present species' range, therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Perseverance near Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Somerset East (Schurfteberg) (-32.73, 25.6). *Northern Cape:* De Aar (-30.64, 24.01); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid is thick, nearly circular except at hinge with the upper surface irregular, concave or nearly flat, coated with mud. The underside is flat or more convex with circle of pits absent or reduced. Sampled from the Nama Karoo and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the present species' range

TAXONOMIC NAME: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

***Stasimopus schultzei* Purcell, 1908**

COMMON NAMES: Schultz's Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1908) from Steinkopf. More recent sampling was made in the Richterveld National Park and Namaqua National Park (EOO= 6 595 km²; AOO=12 km²; 14-870 m a.s.l.). However, the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Richterveld National Park (-28.5872, 16.5181); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Desert and Succulent biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Stasimopus spinipes Hewitt, 1917

COMMON NAMES: East London Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1917) and known only from type locality East London (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 56 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape*: East London (-33.01, 27.9).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Ticket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes, with photographs provided.

After Hewitt (1917)

Stasimopus spinosus Hewitt, 1914

COMMON NAMES: Keiskamma Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1914) as *Stasimopus schönlandi spinosus* from Annshaw. Known from four localities but all sampled prior to 1914 (EOO=1 182 km²; AOO=16 km²; 474-860 m a.s.l.). However, the status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the present species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Alice (-32.78, 26.82); Annshaw (-31.95, 27.42); Debe Neck (-32.49, 27.09); Middeldrift (-32.82, 26.98).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Thicket Biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

***Stasimopus steynburgensis* Hewitt, 1915**

COMMON NAMES: Steynburg Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described Hewitt (1915) and only known from type locality Steynsburg (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 1462 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Steynsburg (-31.29, 25.83).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the male.

***Stasimopus suffuscus* Hewitt, 1916**

COMMON NAMES: Heidelberg Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Beerlaagte near Heidelberg (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1522 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Beerlaagte, Heidelberg (-26.78, 28.43)

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Know only from the female. Eyes unusually small; posterior median eyes rounded; carapace and legs chestnut brown TL female 33 mm.

***Stasimopus tysoni* Hewitt, 1919**

COMMON NAMES: Port Alfred Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described Hewitt (1919) and known only from type locality Port Alfred (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 59 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Thicket Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

***Stasimopus unispinosus* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAMES: De Aar Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described in 1903 from De Aar. Presently known from two localities both sampled prior to 1903 (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 1242-1358 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Farm Poortjesfontein, De Aar (-30.64, 24.01); Hanover (-30.94, 24.53).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid is very thick 6-8 mm thick and cork-like and not strongly beveled at edge with lower edge more rounded. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from both sexes, not illustrated.

***Stasimopus umtaticus* Purcell, 1903**

COMMON NAMES: Umtata Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1903) from Umtata. (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 671-674 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Umtata (-31.58, 28.77).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. Sampled from the Grassland and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

***Stasimopus umtaticus rangeri* Hewitt, 1927**

COMMON NAMES: Cork-Lid Trapdoor Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1927) from the farm Gleniffer near Kei Road station. (EOO < 100 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 1242-1358 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Farm Gleniffer near Kei Road Station (-32.7, 27.54).

LIFESTYLE: Ground dweller living in silk-lined burrows closed with a cork-lid trapdoor. The lid is very thick 6-8 mm thick and cork-like and not strongly beveled at edge with lower edge more rounded. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to this species are unknown. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

REFERENCES

- AUSSERER A 1871. Beiträge zur Kenntniss der Arachniden-Familie der Territelariae Thorell (Mygalidae Autor). *Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien* 21: 117-224.
- BOLD T 2008. Xhosa use of trapdoor spiders. *SANSA News* 8: 11.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S 2002. *Baboon and Trapdoor spiders of Southern Africa: an identification manual*. Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook series no. 13, Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria. 130 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publisher, 424 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S & JOCQUÉ R 1997. *African spiders, an identification manual*. Biosystematics Division, ARC-Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria. Handbook 9, 392 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S, VAN DEN BERG A M & VAN DEN BERG A 1989. Species composition and relative seasonal abundance of spiders from the field and tree layers of the Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve. *Koedoe* 32: 51-60.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S, LEROY A, DE JAGER M & VAN DEN BERG A. 1999. Spider diversity of the Karoo National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Koedoe* 42: 31-42.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S, FOORD S H, HADDAD C.R. & LER ROUX E. 2021 A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Bontbok National Park in the Western Cape Province, South Africa. *SANSA News* 38: 14-22.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S, VAN DER WALT A E, DE JAGER M, LE ROUX E AND VAN DEN BERG A 2005. The spiders of the Swartberg Nature Reserve in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *Koedoe* 48: 77-86.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S, JONES A, HADDAD C R & LOTZ L. 2021 Grassland Spiders of Mpetsane Conservation Estate in the Free State (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA News* 38: 23-32.
- ENGELBRECHT I & PRENDINI L 2012. Cryptic diversity of South African trapdoor spiders: three new species of *Stasimopus* Simon, 1892 (Mygalomorphae, Ctenizidae), and redescription of *Stasimopus robertsi* Hewitt, 1910. *American Museum Novitates* 3732: 1-42.
- FOORD S H, DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S & HADDAD C R 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170-201.
- HADDAD C & BUTLER V P 2018. Ground-dwelling spider assemblages in contrasting habitats in the central South African Grassland Biome. *Koedoe* 60(1), a1482. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v60i1.1482>.
- HADDAD C R & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S 2006. Spiders (Araneae) inhabiting abandoned mounds of the snouted harvester termite *Trinervitermes trinervoides* (Sjöstedt) (Isoptera: Termitidae: Nasutitermitinae) in the Free State, South Africa, with notes on their biology. *Navorsing van die nasionale Museum, Bloemfontein* 22(1): 1-15.
- HADDAD C R, DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S, FOORD S H, LOTZ L N & LYLE R 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97-122.
- HADDAD C R, FOORD S H, FOURIE R & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A S 2015. Effects of a fast-burning spring fire on the ground-dwelling spider assemblages (Arachnida: Araneae) in a central South African grassland habitat. *African Zoology* 50: 281-292.
- HENDRIXSON B E & BOND J E 2004. A new species of *Stasimopus* from the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa (Araneae, Mygalomorphae, Ctenizidae), with notes on its natural history. *Zootaxa* 619: 1-14.
- HEWITT J 1913. Descriptions of new and little known species of trapdoor spiders (Ctenizidae and Migidae) from South Africa. *Records of the Albany Museum Grahamstown* 2: 404-434.
- HEWITT J 1914. Descriptions of new Arachnida from South Africa. *Records of the Albany Museum Grahamstown* 3: 1-37.

REFERENCES

- HEWITT J. 1915. Notes on several four-lunged spiders in the collection of the Durban Museum, with descriptions of two new forms. *Annals of the Durban Museum* 1: 125-133.
- HEWITT J 1915. Descriptions of new South African Arachnida. *Records of the Albany Museum Grahamstown* 3: 70-106.
- HEWITT J 1917. Descriptions of new South African Arachnida. *Annals of the Natal Museum* 3: 687-711.
- HEWITT J 1919. Descriptions of new South African Araneae and Solifugae. *Annals of the Transvaal Museum* 6: 63-111.
- HEWITT J 1927. On some new arachnids from South Africa. *Records of the Albany Museum Grahamstown* 3: 416-429.
- KARSCH F 1879. Zur Theraphosiden-Gattung Moggridgea. *Zeitschrift für die Gesammten Naturwissenschaften* 52: 383-385.
- KOCH C L 1842. *Die Arachniden*. Nürnberg, Neunter Band, pp. 57-108, Zehnter Band, 1-3.
- NEETHLING J A & HADDAD C R 2019. Influence of some abiotic factors on the activity patterns of trapdoor spiders, scorpions and camel spiders in a central South African grassland. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 74: 107-114.
- PICKARD-CAMBRIDGE O. 1889. On some new species and a new genus of Araneida. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 57(1): 34-46, PL. II.
- POCOCK R I 1898. The Arachnida from the province of Natal, South Africa, contained in the collection of the British Museum. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (7) 2: 197-226.
- POCOCK R I 1900. Some new Arachnida from Cape Colony. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (7) 6: 316-333.
- POCOCK R I 1901. Descriptions of some new African Arachnida. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, (7) 7: 284-288.
- POCOCK R I 1902. Some new African spiders. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (7) 10: 315-330.
- POCOCK R I 1902. Descriptions of some new species of African Solifugae and Araneae. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* (7) 10: 6-27.
- POCOCK R I 1902 On some new African spiders. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History* 7(10): 315-330.
- PURCELL W F 1902. New South African trap-door spiders of the family Ctenizidae in the collection of the South African Museum. *Transactions of the South African Philosophical Society* 11: 348-382.
- PURCELL W F 1903a. On the scorpions, solifugae and a trap-door spider collected by the Rev. Henry A. Junod at Shiluvane, near Leydsdorp, in the Transvaal. *Novitates zoologicae* 10: 303-306.
- PURCELL W F 1903b. New South African spiders of the families Migidae, Ctenizidae, Barychelidae Dipluridae, and Lycosidae. *Annals of the South African Museum* 3: 69-142.
- PURCELL W F 1908. Araneae. In: Schultze, L. (ed.) *Forschungsreise in Südafrika*, 1(2). *Denkschriften der Medizinisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Gesellschaft zu Jena* 13: 203-246.
- RAVEN R J 1985. The spider infraorder Mygalomorphae (Araneae): Cladistics and systematics. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 182: 1-180.
- RAVEN R J 1994. Mygalomorph spiders of the Barychelidae in Australia and the Western Pacific. *Memoirs of the Queensland Museum* 35: 291-706.
- SIMON E 1892. *Histoire naturelle des araignées*. Paris 1: 1-256.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2021. World Spider Catalog. Version 22.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 2 May 2021 doi: 10.24436/2